

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE COMMISSIONER-JUDGE IN THE INDONESIA'S CRIMINAL JUSTICE SYSTEM

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Abstract

The discussion on Commissioner-judges in the Criminal Code Bill from the Ministry of Law and Human Rights states that the current commissioners have the same authority as pre-trial proceedings except the authority to extend detention and pre-trial which decides whether a case is appropriate or not submitted to the court at the request of the prosecutor. Based on this statement, this paper will explore how the application of commissioner-judges in the criminal procedural law process can be implemented effectively in Indonesia. This research is explored more deeply through normative juridical studies which are strengthened by the dominance of literature review. This study concludes that the presence of the commissioner-judge in the criminal process becomes an effort on providing information in the event of errors related to law enforcement from the engineering of criminal cases which affect the human rights of the accused. Human Rights as the basis and legitimacy of the practice of commissioner-judges is essential since it depends on a comparison of the implementation by several other countries, meaning that currently, the House of Representatives must accelerate and hasten changes to the Criminal Procedure Code and be ratified into a formal legal system can be carried out by all law enforcers.

A. INTRODUCTION

The State is obliged to provide justice for the community, because law enforcement is dominated by the hands of country's power, and the main goal of creating law is making the community happy (the greatest happiness for the greatest number of people). This argument must be in line with 3 (three) main legal objectives, namely certainty, justice and legal benefit. ¹The notion on reforming criminal law is needed to actualize that imposing punishment is intended for a peaceful and safe community life. When criminal objective is achieved, consequently the law enforcement will run properly and fairly. This becomes important to realize as a protection of Human Rights (HAM) from violations conducted by law enforcers themselves

Changes of the Criminal Code and the criminal procedure law draft (RKUHP and RKUHAP) are becoming the first step to achieve real and tangible criminal goals changes. Afterwards, it will affect the change of law enforcement practices, bureaucracy, social life, and others. Moreover, this change is also intended for the protection of human right to live in the life of the nation and state. Currently, the Criminal Procedure Code (KUHAP) still has many shortcomings, one of them is the practice of pre-trial institutions, the criminal procedural law process regulated in Article 77, the rigid regulation in the authority of pre-trial judge who have limitations in deciding whether the arrest of a person is legal or illegitimate. Both the arrest process and the criminal procedural legal process related to detention, termination of investigation and prosecution are also regulated in Article 77 to Article 83 of the Criminal Procedure Code.

The weakness of pre-trial institutions is not only seen from its limited authority, but also from the practice itself, meaning that the institution can only wait for a lawsuit from the existing formal truth. In fact, even the pre-trial institution has not run as musr. According to Hamzah, the idea of pre-trial emerged from the Habeas Corpus right, a Fundamental Guarantee Rights in a Human Rights to the Independence right. The rights are used to protect someone who has been suspected of committing a crime from the unauthorized examination.² As an effort to protect Human Rights of criminal act in the draft of Criminal Procedure Code, which is being discussed by the Ministry of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia, the Commissioner-judge is proposed as an alternative for the Pre-trial institution that has many substance and material weaknesses. Although the presence of Commissioner-judges is remained debateable, but it has become a special public concern since the discussion of human rights must be long lasting, thoroughly and comprehensively, even the pre-trial institutions often override human rights themselves. To provide a comprehensive view, this research departs from the question of how important the existence of commissioner-judges is in Indonesia from legal science perspective, then what should be done by the Indonesian government in determining Commissioner-judges

B. RESEARCH METHOD

This study applies a normative juridical research method, indicates that all existing regulations become the basis for a study related to practice of commissioner-judges in Indonesia, whether or not it is fully applicable. In addition to be an object of study, its practice is also studied through a comparative approach. Therefore, the research cannot be separated from the basics of normative and comparative approaches within the scope of legal science including legal principles, synchronization of laws and regulations, and legal discovery (inconcreto).

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Theoretical Application Concept Of Commissioner-Judge In Indonesia

The doctrine of "communias opinion doctorum" for the current criminal system has not succeeded in achieving its goals, neither particularly for perpetrators and victims, nor for society in general. Some argues that the criminal system has failed to realize the purpose of punishment. For instance, the ideal punishment for the perpetrator is to have a good reason and responsibility, while the fact shows they still keep on repeating the crime (recidivists). Statistically, there is possibility for the inmates of a penitentiary are balanced between repeat offenders and non-recurrent offenders. On the day of release, there are even some perpetrators who immediately committed another crime.

There used to be an expression that prison is an "academy of crime" where they learn to be more skilled at committing crimes. It is found that some ex-convicts are forced to repeat criminal acts due to facing difficult life while the surrounding community does not help to provide meal for them. One of the problems faced by ex-convicts is the dislike and hostility of the community. Ex-convicts become isolated people, which causes various difficulties for easily repeating crime

Hans Kelsen is one of the scholars who distinguishes between autocracy and democracy in terms of law-making.³ Kelsen's view is a normative aspect of the democracy concept because it sees freedom concerning the law formation. According to the positive and negative freedom, juristic democracy can be classified into 2 (two) models of democracy; constitutional democracy and participatory democracy. Freedom in a negative concept that glorifies individual freedom and rejects all restrictions on freedom has given birth to constitutional democracy, while the concept of freedom in a positive sense that emphasizes equality of degrees to explore self-potential gives birth to participatory democracy.

Constitutional democracy is a model of democracy that emphasizes representative institutions and constitutional procedures. Democracy is characterized by free competition which opens up opportunities for constitutional changes to take place on an ongoing basis. These changes are carried out through general elections which give birth to a people's representative institution. Thus, the rule of majority is applied in the state management. Finally, the constitutional democracy emphasizes fully on procedural aspects to ignore morals. This is suitable to a free market economy or laissez-faire which believes there is a hidden hand in regulating the operation of the mechanism. Constitutional democracy requires a "minimal state" that gives complete freedom to individuals by limiting country's power as much as possible. From a legal point of view, this concept of democracy is known as a formal law state or a night watch state.⁴

The use of John Rawl's justice theory as the basis of the Middle range theory and the theory of "restorative justice" as a universal cultural phenomenon is in line which Braith Waite said:

"They are universals because they are au vital to our emotional survival as human beings and vital to possibility of surviving without constant fear of violence. The world's great religions recognize that desire to persue the restorative justice value is universal, which is why our spiritual leaders are hope against those political leaders who wish to rule through fear and by crushing deliberate democracy⁵.

Conceptually, the substance of the "restorative justice" theory is containing 4 (four) ideas and 6 (six) principles as follows:

- a. Build joint participation between perpetrators, victims and community groups to resolve a crime. Placing them as "stakeholders" who work together and immediately try to find win-win solutions.
- b. Encouraging the perpetrator to be responsible for the victim of crime that has caused injury or loss to the victim then build the responsibility of not repeating it
- c. Placing a criminal act not primarily as a form of violation of the law but as a violation by a person (a group of people against a person/group of people). because of this, the perpetrator should be directed to accountability for the victim, not prioritizing legal responsibility.
- d. Encouraging the completion of a criminal act in more informal and personal ways and in resolving it in formal (rigid) and impersonal ways.⁶

There are 6 (six) main principles of a restorative justice framework as follows:

- a. The criminal act is a human behaviour in the form of a violation of social relations, both personal and against other parties. It is not merely violations of state law but violations against people.
- b. The aim of the Judiciary is to quickly repair the damage and restore relations, both to individuals and society to their previous condition
- c. Victims should have the chance to take part in the process. participation can be in the form of information and dialogue with perpetrators, reciprocal settlements with perpetrators regarding restitution (compensation), reducing fear, increasing a sense of peace, the growth of new hopes, and so on.
- d. The perpetrator is allowed to accept his responsibilities and obligations towards the victim and society in general. Participation can be in the form of determining obligations, dealing directly with victims, understanding the impact of actions, and so on
- e. The surrounding (local) community and its sources must express the various needs of victims and perpetrators, including the prevention of violations.
- f. The formal criminal justice system must ensure that victims and perpetrators engage in values that bind all participants without any coercion, including monitoring

How the mechanism implements two concepts that need to be considered, First; momentum before entering the judicial process or as part of the judicial process and the two forums used. "restorative justice" often translated as restorative justice,⁷ is a model approach that emerged in the 1960s era in efforts to resolve criminal cases. This is different from the approach used in the conventional criminal justice system, which focuses on the direct participation of perpetrators, victims and the community in the process of resolving criminal cases. Although this approach is still theoretically debated, this view has evolved and has influenced legal policy and practice in many countries.

Handling criminal cases with a restorative justice approach offer different views and approaches to understanding handling a criminal act. Generally, in the restorative justice perspective the word of crimes has the same meaning as in the criminal law, which are attacks on individuals, society, and social relations.⁸ In the restorative justice approach, the main victim for the occurrence of a crime is not by the state, as in the current criminal justice system, because crime creates an obligation to repair damaged relationships. The purpose of justice is interpreted as a process of finding solutions to problems that occur in a criminal case where the involvement of victims, communities and perpetrators is important in efforts to repair, reconcile and guarantee the continuity of these repair efforts. As the most up-to-date approach in criminal law, the United Nations outlines through the Basic Principles approach that has been outlined assessing a restorative justice approach can be used in a rational criminal justice system. In line with the views of G.P. Hoefnagels who stated that a rational total of the responses to crime.⁹ The restorative justice approach is a paradigm can be used as a framework

for a criminal case handling strategy that aims to address dissatisfaction with the current criminal justice system. The understanding of restorative justice is a new form of approach can be used in handling criminal cases, as illustrated by the definition that will be put forward by Dignan as follows.

“Restorative justice is a new framework for responding to wrongdoing and conflict that is rapidly accepted and supported by educational, legal, social work, and counseling professionals and community groups. Restorative justice is a valued-based approach to responding to wrongdoing and conflict with a balanced focus on the person harmed, the person causing the harm, and the affected community”

This definition requires certain conditions that place restorative justice as the basic value used in responding to a criminal case which requires a balance of focus of attention between the interests of the perpetrator and the victim and also takes into account the impact of the settlement of criminal cases in society. The application of this requirement is not easy considering the mainstream thinking of law enforcement officers who have been patterned with the conventional line of thinking of the current criminal justice system as mentioned by Mark Umbreit':¹⁰

"restorative justice provides a very different framework for understanding and responding to crime. Crime is understood as harm to individuals and communities, rather than simply violation of abstract laws against the state. those most directly affected by crime victims, community members, and offenders- a, therefore, encouraged to play an active role in the justice process rather than the current focus on offender punishment, restorative of the emotional and material losses resulting from crime is far important."

The weakness of the current criminal justice system is regarding the neglected victims and the public interests. In the criminal case settlement model using a restorative justice approach, the active role of both parties becomes important in addition to the role of the perpetrator. Many writers consider restorative justice not a new concept, perhaps as old as Criminal law itself. Even thousands of years ago, the effort to handle criminal cases is placed as the main mechanism for handling criminal acts. Marc Levin argues that the approach that was once declared obsolete, ancient and traditional is now being declared as a progressive approach.¹¹ Hooker describes the universal elements that form the basis and system of customary law as follows:¹²

- a. The distribution of obligation is often a function of an actual or putative genealogical relationship;
- b. The Community, whether defined on a genealogical or a territorial basis, almost always has a greater right over land distribution than the individual prosesor or occuppies.
- c. The Institution of mutual of cooperation and exemplify the individual's subjection to a common set the obligations
- d. The adats position the preservation of harmony between the community and nature.

The concept of Indonesian customary law as a forum and institution for customary justice also has a concept that can be described as the root of restorative justice. In Indonesia, the characteristics of customary law in each region strongly support the application of restorative justice. It can be seen from the general characteristics of Indonesian customary law and views on customary violations/offenses as well as the models and methods of settlement offered. A simple model of the restorative justice approach already exists in Indonesian society where the resolution of conflicts that arise is carried out by means of deliberation. This model in the language of "restorative justice" is known as the conference, circle or Victim-Offender Mediation (VOM) model. The position of the victim, and the community becomes a problem in the construction of the existing criminal justice process since the context of their participation in a criminal case settlement is mostly outside the system or better known as out of Court Settlement, which then causes the need for a shift or adjustment of principles.

a. Ius Punale and ius Puniendi

The current justice approach and the criminal justice system shows different perspective. On the one hand, full state authority over sentencing has created a criminal justice system that is only oriented towards resolving criminal cases through one route through the criminal justice process. As restorative justice, with the developed paradigm, it opens up opportunities for alternative criminal case settlements through other channels outside the criminal justice system, including direct, free, and independent mediation and reconciliation in determining the model for resolving criminal cases that is considered the best and fairest.

b. Nuua poena sine lege

The approach to resolving criminal cases is not remained a state monopoly but also part of the authority of each individual to find the best mechanism and solution for the legal conflicts faced, so the type of tolerance for sanctions becomes very open where the types and forms can be in the form of agreements that occur between parties. perpetrator and victim.

A change in approach means a change in mindset, towards the function of criminal law as the ultimum remedium, or it has an impact on system. The translation of the Criminal Justice System (CJS) shows the working mechanism in carrying out the function of criminal law in overcoming criminal acts using a systems approach as proposed by Remington and Oblin. CJS can be interpreted as the use of a systems approach to the mechanism of criminal justice administration. As a system, criminal justice is the result of the interaction between statutory regulations, administrative practices, and social attitudes or behavior. Understanding the system itself implies an interaction process that is prepared rationally in an efficient manner to provide certain results with all limitations.¹³ Mardjono Reksodiputro requires that this system has a purpose, namely.

- a. Preventing people from becoming victims of crime;
- b. Resolving crime cases in the community so people got satisfied that justice has been upheld and the guilty are punished
- c. Ensuring those who have committed crimes do not repeat their crimes.¹⁴

To achieve the objectives as required by Mardjono Reksodiputro, the criminal justice system works as a network, and the material criminal law, formal criminal law, and criminal law enforcement are used as its sub-systems,. In Indonesia, the applicable criminal justice system is regulated in Law Number 8 of 1981, which systemically regulates, directs or gives instructions to law enforcement officers who are in the sub-criminal justice system. In this law, the criminal justice sub-systems referred to are the police, prosecutors, courts and correctional institutions. In the view that is currently developing, the criminal justice sub-system works based only on the provisions stipulated in the law. The purpose of the system also leads to what emphasizes legal certainty.

The changes on the public reactions view as changes in views on criminal acts and perpetrators of criminal acts made the mechanism of the working of the criminal justice system changed with the mindset that exists in a development where the relationship between the work of the criminal justice system is not only part of the state's response to a norms violation, but also a picture of how society sees it. According to John Rawls' belief or "Justice is fairness", the justice needs to be formalized through the constitution and law as the basis for the implementation of individual rights and obligations in social interaction or formal justice according to minimum equality for the whole community.¹⁵

Although formal justice is required, it does not fully support and encourage a well-ordered society. A concept of justice can only effectively regulate society when it is generally accepted, and provides equal treatment for all members of society who are accommodated in regulatory justice, which contains the recognition of freedom and equality for all. While formal justice tends to be imposed unilaterally, especially must be avoided by the authorities. Hence, it is necessary to take further steps beyond formal justice to the formulation of a theory of justice that gives place to all parties who are reached by certain public policies.

Rawls, as a theory of justice, is believed to be consistent which guarantees all parties fairly.¹⁶ Justice must also be interpreted as fairness, meaning that social benefits can not only entitled to people who gave better services, but these must also belong to basic human to improve their life prospects. On the application of justice as fairness, Rawls requires three things: first, the moral person as the basis for the concept of justice, asserts that the basic moral person is characterized by two moral abilities, namely:

- a. The ability to act based on a sense of justice and with it also encouraged to seek a social cooperation, and
- b. The ability to form, revise and rationally strive for the realization of a good concept, which encourages everyone to strive for the fulfillment of primary values and benefits for himself.¹⁷

These two forms of moral ability possessed by each person strengthen the individual as a rational, free and equal person. These moral abilities also enable each person to act properly on the principles of justice, rational and autonomous, apply appropriate means and goals for himself, also these moral abilities function as the appropriate and realizable motivation and value in oneself. The view that the moral person as the basis of the concept of justice reflects

the basic beliefs and views of humans as moral persons who are free, rational and equal in nature

2. Terminology And Implementation Of Commissioner-Judges In The Criminal Justice System

The Commissioner-judge plays an active role prior to the implementation of coercive measures from investigators and prosecutors in the form of arrest, detention, confiscation of evidence, body searches, entry of residence or other places, even determining whether or not sufficient evidence is submitted in a criminal justice process. Regarding the adequacy of evidence, this is intended as one way to minimize the flow of cases in the criminal process.

Moreover, they can act proactively on the issue of torture or violence against a suspect/defendant who is in detention who is subjected to violent torture. The passive function of the pre-trial institution which cannot touch this issue. The innovative attitude of the commissioner-judge is to determine whether or not there is a strong suspicion of torture or violence against the suspect the presence within one day of the suspect who is in detention status is mandatory. On the other hand, if it is also an obligation for the investigator/prosecutor to bring the suspect before the commissioner-judge within that period, with the threat of being released by law from detention if they are unable to present him in court.

Regarding commissioner-judges, it seems that the draft (revised) KUHAP intends to imitate the model applied by the Dutch, which was also known in the period before the KUHAP, namely Reglement od de strafvoeding. ¹⁸ (Sv) and is called the rechter-commissaris's authority includes, being able to carry out investigative actions to summon people, witnesses and suspects, visit witnesses' homes and also check whether law enforcement officers are carrying out their duties properly. However, after the HIR took effect, the rechter commissaris was no longer known.

The role of commissioners in the criminal justice system is always a point of departure, therefore they always participate in "controlling" meaning assessing what is done by the agencies in the system that handled previous cases according to their respective authorities, namely the police and the prosecutor's office. In the pre-adjudication phase, the commissioner oversees the investigation in the form of a magistrate or justice of the piece position where they will assess whether there is a probable cause for the alleged existence of a crime and the reasonableness in carrying out detention by investigators is true. Even commissioner-judges were once known as investigating commissioners or also called juge d 'instruction in France, uncschungsrichter in Germany, or conducting investigations into criminal cases. The concept is as a counterweight to the very dominant power of the public prosecutor and as a master of the procedure in French criminal justice. According to Oemar Seno Adji, the Commissioner-judge is the one who leads the preliminary examination but does not conduct the examiner himself. The Commissioner deals with how coercion is carried out. Thus, he is the prosecutor's supervision of the police according to the sources of the previous criminal procedure law.

Principally, the position of "rechter commissaris" that existed in Indonesia which previously in criminal procedure law was applied to European groups, whn it was included in the future

criminal procedure law, then they will be placed next to the prosecutor's office. However, without interfering with the authority of the prosecutor, by not carrying out the preliminary examination himself, in parallel with the prosecutor's authority to supervise coordinating police duties, the "rechter commissaris" has the authority to oversee the implementation of measures or not by law. For example, to monitor whether the detention carried out by the prosecutor is contrary to the law or the actions taken by the prosecutor are in accordance with the law, the confiscation carried out by the prosecutor is in accordance with the law. What needs to be carefully remembered is that in principle, the rechter commissaris has limited authority to supervise, so his relationship with the prosecutor is a parallel between the relationship between the prosecutor and the police.

Some important things about the Commissioner-judge that need to be considered are as follows, First, that the Commissioner is not appropriate when viewed from the perspective of action having a passive nature, meaning that they must be pro-active in researching and reviewing in depth the legality or illegitimacy of a detention. Moreover, he needs to know whether there is a legal termination of the investigation when the suspected does not have sufficient initial evidence elements. The Commissioner focuses on the practice of Cancellation and Suspension of Detention of a suspect, whether it has a legal process or the detention is appropriate for 25 days. Afterwards, the commissioner-judge will see whether the information made by the suspect or the defendant violated the right not to answer. Stating evidence or statements obtained illegally cannot be used as evidence. Then compensation and/or rehabilitation for someone who is illegally arrested or detained or compensation for any confiscated property rights.

Suspects and defendants have the right to or are required to be accompanied by a lawyer. Termination and prosecution are carried out based on the principle of opportunity (opportunities). The main thing the commissioner-judge needs to see the violation of the rights of any other suspect that occurs during the investigation stage. From the various important notes above, it is undeniable the legislators in this case the House of Representatives (DPR) together with the Ministry of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia need to accelerate the process of legalizing the draft Criminal Code into law in force in Indonesia. at least the implementation of the Criminal Code goes straight by accelerating Human Rights which can be protected quickly, and that is the responsibility of the state, to achieve a welfare state.

D. CONCLUSION

The presence of the Commissioner-judge in deciding the draft of the Criminal Procedure Code is a must, considering its existence is an inseparable part of the judicial process against a defendant, they can carry out supervision and can also protect for the human rights of suspects and defendants. From the investigation process, prosecution in the examination process. Therefore, the government together with the House of Representatives (DPR) can ratify the draft KUHP law into law with the passing of the Criminal Code law; it means that Indonesia really accommodates fundamental human rights. This is in line with the legal system in

Indonesia, which prioritizes civil law, rather than other legal systems, which also continue to be used to a degree that is not more dominant than the civil law legal system in Indonesia, for example the Islamic legal system and the common law legal system. In Indonesia, the law becomes maximal if it has been codified by the government, meaning that it has been positive in the norms that apply in a country. Not only does the rule of law greatly support the smooth running of the state government system of law which is embodied in a text and recognized by all the people, the government has played an active role in the welfare of its people for better conditions and conditions in terms of law, no one else can manipulate cases or violate the law and violate the law because the draft criminal law and criminal procedure have been legalized by the state.

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